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Employee-Based Brand Equity of University, Vietnam

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Abstract:

The article conducts an overview of research studies related to university branding, employee-based brand equity of university. From there, the author synthesizes and analyzes to find research gaps and proposes a research model for the University of University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam.

Keywords: *Employee-based brand equity, Vietnam*

1. Introduction

In a market economy, production and distribution exist according to the laws of objective competition. Enterprises are free to produce, goods are introduced to the market more and more and Vietnamese society has entered a new stage. Everyone has the right to choose the use of society's products. Since then, each business must determine for themselves a place in the hearts of consumers, so that every time, thinking of that type of goods, consumers immediately think of their products. There are many factors that attract customers, in which quality is the leading factor, besides price, design and especially customers today pay a lot of attention to convenience and service to the interest of the business, to the "after-sales".

Thus, whether or not customers think about the products of the manufacturers will determine the success or failure of the enterprise's production and business. Therefore, building a brand is indispensable for every business in general and especially for universities.

Brand building and development is a regular part of leadership and management of universities in advanced countries around the world. However, in Vietnam, due to the view of subsidies and the lack of competition in higher education because demand outstrips supply, the issue of university branding has not been given due attention.

The article reviews the theoretical bases for building the employee-based university brand model.

2. Research model and hypothesis

2.1. Lecturer capacity and scientific research results

Each individual has different abilities and to measure individual ability, since the 1960s John L. Efoland and Leonard L. Baird (1968) have built a capacity scale system including 18 factors. element. A person's personal capacity is also influenced by many factors such as: knowledge, skills, self-concept, characteristics and motivation (Muhammad Aiman Arifin et al., 2017); Personal capacity is also assessed as the intersection between knowledge, skills and behavior of a person (To Van Binh, 2016). The teaching staff of the recruited universities must meet the conditions of personal capacity as well as faculty capacity to ensure the quality of training in the universities. The capacity of lecturers is always concerned by university leaders because lecturers are a team that directly teaches knowledge to students, often interacts with students in courses, modules, and programs. training (Nguyen Dinh Tho, Nguyen Thi Mai Trang, 2010). Lecturers in universities, in addition to the personal capacity of each person, are also influenced by the conditions to form a teacher's profession such as: teaching capacity, professional capacity, communication capacity and personal capacity. individuals

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(Muhammad Aiman Bin Arifin et al., 2017); impact of work performance, skills, ethics, tasks and personal problems (Aliasghar Mashinchi et al., 2017).

Thus, the capacity of lecturers is formed from two factors: personal capacity and capacity to become lecturers in universities and it is from the capacity of lecturers that have an impact on the activities of lecturers. school, in which the activity associated with the faculty's capacity is scientific research. Scientific research activities are also specified and codified into a specific provision in the higher education law (higher education law, 2012) for lecturers to perform in addition to their main teaching duties. also carry out scientific research. The scientific research and the results of the scientific research tasks are influenced and influenced by the capacity of the lecturers. According to Emmanuel Chinamasa (2012), scientific research activities are motivated by factors such as wanting to own scientific research results, wanting to be promoted. He also affirmed that the factors affecting the output of scientific research as well as the results of scientific research are influenced by part of the capacity of lecturers. Therefore, the author put forward the research hypothesis H1 as follows:

H1: The capacity of lecturers has a direct impact on the results of scientific research

2.2. Faculty capacity and university brand

Lecturer is considered a profession like other professions, lecturers also work in an organization called university or higher education institution. After being recruited, each lecturer will be officially employed in a higher education institution which is called a permanent lecturer of the school (Law on Higher Education, 2012). According to Michael Proksch, Ulrich R. Orth and T. Bettina Cornwell (2015) believe that capacity building will have a positive impact on an organization's brand. The faculty working in each school strives to fulfill their assigned tasks and it is in the completion of that task that contributes to the prestige of the university brand (Michael Proksch, Ulrich R. Orth and T. Bettina Cornwell, 2015). Thus, the capacity of lecturers is also an important factor to build and develop the university brand, so the author proposes the research hypothesis H2 as follows:

H2: Faculty competence has a direct impact on employee-based university brand

2.3. Scientific research results and university brand

Scientific research work is the duty of lecturers, which are specified by universities on the length of scientific research for each academic year, each semester (Law on Higher Education, 2012). The duration of the lecturer's scientific research is a factor that plays an important role in the scientific research results of the lecturer. According to the statistics of Duy Tan University (2018), the scientific research results of universities are still very low, especially research works published in prestigious international journals are limited in terms of science and technology. In many aspects, the total number of published research works over 100 works is only 18/235 universities in Vietnam (accounting for a very low rate, only 7.66%). The results of scientific research are also a criterion to evaluate the educational quality of universities. The Ministry of Education and Training has included the results of scientific research into a criterion in the set of standards for assessment and accreditation of education quality at the educational institution level (Circular 12/2017/TT-BGDDT dated May 19, 2017) and training program (Circular 04/2016/TT-BGDDT dated 14/03/2016). Internationally, the results of scientific research have been established by the Association of Southeast Asian Universities (AUN - QA) into a standard for accrediting schools and training programs despite having gone through three years. Although the standard of scientific research results has been revised and supplemented several times, it has been retained for assessment purposes (Guide to AUN-QA Assessment at Program Level, Version 3.0, 2015). In addition, the number of published scientific research works is also recognized by the world's leading university ranking organizations such as Times Higher Education (THE); Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) and Shanghai Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU) review to rank universities.

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Thus, a university that is accredited for education quality at any level (junior level or program level) or ranked by university ranking organizations proves that the quality of training meets the needs of students. requirements of society, training for society with good quality human resources, thereby enhancing the university's brand value. Therefore, the author put forward the research hypothesis H3 as follows:

H3: Scientific research results have a direct impact on employee-based university brand

2.4. Role clarity, brand commitment and university brand

The Institute is clearly aware of the individual's role in the organization, brand commitment helps individuals work more effectively, is more satisfied and thereby leads to positive word of mouth about the organization, i.e. increased prices. Employee-based branding for the organization. From the clarity of the role makes employees have brand commitment behavior. Therefore, the author put forward the following research hypothesis:

H4: Role clarity of a direct positive impact on employee-based university brand

H5: Brand commitment has a direct positive impact on employee-based university branding

H6: Role clarity has a direct positive impact on brand commitment

2.5. University brand and university performance

Brand, also known as brand equity, is, by its very nature, an intangible asset of an organization. In higher education too, brand equity, or brand equity – employee-based brand equity improves organizational performance. Therefore, the author proposes the research hypothesis

H7: Employee-based university branding has a positive impact on university performance.

3. Research model and conclusion

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Figure 1. Research model

During the first decade of the 21st century, growing interest in organizational branding stemmed from the simple assumption that an investment in organizational image would have positive results across all sectors and not just the bottom line. from the customer point of view but also from the employee point of view (Fetscherin and Usunier, 2012). Organizational branding is considered an appropriate branding strategy in the service sector because organizational branding offers many benefits, including information about the values of that brand, a means to differentiation from competitors and respect and loyalty from stakeholder groups (Balmer, 2001). Like many service organizations, universities are facing an increasingly competitive environment in which they must find ways to differentiate themselves (Judson et al., 2009). A university brand is an attractive name, image, and description of an institution that captures the essence of the value that the university offers (Fredericks and Parmley, 2000). In the context of a university as a complex institution, branding can simplify this complexity and increase attraction and loyalty to the institution (Bulotaite, 2003). Branding in higher education helps students and their parents identify specific services offered and motivate them to use (Harvey, 1996). The University of Houston decided to launch a \$5 million, five-year campaign to build an image, a proactive approach (Hacker, 2005). Similarly, Point Park University in Pittsburg announced a \$1 million branding campaign through billboards, newspaper ads, and other media (Schackner, 2004). Universities around the world have increasingly implemented integrated marketing techniques in strengthening their promotion efforts.

In general, the strategic importance of having a strong organizational brand in the education sector has been recognized by the administrators of many universities (Balmer and Liao, 2007; Judson et al., 2009). However, so far, branding in higher education is still a controversial issue, there is very little research on branding in higher education and not much attention from researchers. academia although there is some research on

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marketing in higher education (Chapleo, 2011). In particular, empirical studies on branding, identity and image in higher education are quite rare (Hemsley-Brown and Goonawardana, 2007).

Research works focus on external marketing specifically such as: student expectations and its impact on satisfaction (Appleton-Knapp and Krentler, 2006); image and reputation of the university in students' decision to continue their studies (Nguyen and LeBlanc, 2001); students' perceptions of quality (Sultan and Wong, 2010; Hill et al., 2003; Chua, 2004); students' motivation to apply for business majors (Bennett, 2004); marketing the organization to potential students (Beneke, 2011); the role of organizational identity (Melewar and Akel, 2005), and to some extent, exploratory branding.

Topics of consumer-based branding in higher education have been published such as: the role of the website in university branding (Opoku et al., 2006); the role of heritage: a tool for branding and marketing (Bulotaite, 2003); the emergence of brand identity (Lowrie, 2007); harmonization within the university's brand architecture (Hemsley-Brown and Goonawardana, 2007); university branding in Asia (Gray et al., 2003); university branding: similarities and differences in identity development (Lowrie, 2007); barriers to university branding (Chapleo, 2007); successful university brand (Chapleo, 2010); measure university branding (Chapleo, 2011). On the approach to university branding from within, there are few studies such as: branding from within: the most valuable intangible asset of a university (Whisman, 2009); building a university brand from within (Judson et al., 2009) and these studies are exploratory.

Overall, there is little research involving employees in the area of internal brand management (King and Grace, 2010). Most of this internal branding research focuses on managers and consultants, although employees are seen as the internal target audience of an internal branding strategy. (Punjaisri et al., 2009). Survey subjects are usually not employees. In particular, very little research has been done on branding in higher education, although its usefulness, relevance, and importance are substantial. Thereby, showing the necessity of research on organizational branding in this field. However, there are many studies that question the suitability of commercial branding concepts for the higher education sector, stemming from the applicability of market principles to education. university and whether commercial branding is really a test of university integrity (Chapleo, 2011). Another important issue raised is that communicating the organizational brand of a university is complex and diverse in nature to many different stakeholders with different feelings. increases the difficulty of branding activities (Chapleo, 2011).

Obviously, any institution faces certain challenges in building and maintaining a strong brand, but the pertinent question is whether there are specific problems that universities face in the future. their branding activities or not (Chapleo, 2007). Similar to the philanthropic sector, there is little academic activity for brands in the education sector because of the "more complexity" and "difficulty in bringing together internal stakeholders to branding concepts" (Chapleo, 2007). Hankinson (2001) argues that a central requirement for successful branding is consistency in what the brand stands for, but the complexity of organization and control erodes this consistency. The author argues that a suitable organizational structure is needed to support brand consistency and this makes sense for brands in universities with rather complex structures. The complexity of this organization can be significantly exacerbated by the diversity in brand management models. Commercially-focused activities such as branding are inherently difficult for universities, as "one must take care of the needs of linking related departments and not just goals commercial" (Chapleo, 2007).

Keller (2003) argues that the customer 'experience' is crucial, while Hankinson (2004) shows the need for an organizational 'behavioral element' in successful branding. This could therefore provide some important ideas for university branding, where employees and their attitudes and behaviors shape the perception of the brand. In the study of Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka (2006), the authors, after synthesizing and analyzing the theoretical basis of relationship marketing, came to the conclusion that participants in higher education "seek to develop development of educational relationships rather than transactions between merchants", and "the economic

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market that converts higher education into a commodity on the basis of trusts acquired in the institution of higher education, as that relationship marketing is compatible with the nature of university (and other) service because this approach fosters employee involvement in meeting student needs and expectations, while encouraging students to actively participate in school activities, improve or maintain university reputation. Relationship marketing is a viable strategy in the not-for-profit context of higher education, where success not only focuses on economic benefits, but also highlights social benefits including emotional satisfaction, spiritual god and share humanistic ideals.

References

- i Nguyen Thi Lien Diep (2012). *Management Studies*, Labor and Social Publishing House.
- ii Pham Minh Hac (2001), *Psychology*, Education Publishing House, Hanoi.
- iii Tran Tien Khoa (2013), *University brand management in the Vietnamese context: from the perspective of brand identity theory*, *Journal of Science and Technology Development*, volume 16, Q2, page 117 -126.
- iv Ngo Thi Nu (2018), *The issue of developing personal capacity of Vietnamese people in the current international integration conditions*, PhD thesis, Ho Chi Minh National Academy of Politics.
- v Nguyen Thac, Pham Thanh Nghi (2011) *University Psychology*, Education Publishing House.
- vi Nguyen Thi Hong Nguyet (2017), *Signal quality and brand-customer relationship in Vietnam's consumer goods market*, PhD thesis, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City.
- vii Nguyen Thi Tinh (2010), *Teaching Activeness of University Lecturers*, Encyclopedia Publishing House, Hanoi.
- viii Nguyen Dinh Tho et al. (2002), *Brand equity components and their measurement in the Vietnamese consumer goods market*.
- ix Nguyen Dinh Tho - Nguyen Thi Mai Trang (2008), *Marketing Scientific Research*, National University Publishing House, Ho Chi Minh City
- x Nguyen Dinh Tho (2011). *Scientific research methods in business – design and implementation*. City. Ho Chi Minh: Labor and Social Publishing House
- xi Nguyen Dinh Tho & Nguyen Thi Mai Trang (2002). *Excerpted from “Keller, KL (2003), Understanding Brands, Branding and Brand Equity, Intercreative Marketing 5(1)”*.
- xii Nguyen Dinh Tho, Nguyen Thi Mai Trang & Barrett (2003). *Brand passion and the factors that affect it*. Ho Chi Minh City Economic Development Magazine, 153: 2-5.
- xiii Nguyen Thanh Trung (2015), *Employee-Based University Brand Value: Research in Vietnam*, Doctoral Thesis, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City.
- xiv Circular 15/2014/TT-BKHCN, dated June 13, 2014, stipulating the order and procedures for assignment of ownership rights and the right to use results of scientific research and technological development using state budget. country.
- xv Circular 47/2014/TT-BGDĐT, dated December 31, 2104, regulating the working regime for lecturers.
- xvi Circular 04/2016/TT-BGDĐT, dated March 14, 2016, of the Ministry of Education and Training promulgating regulations on standards for assessing the quality of training programs at higher education levels.
- xvii Circular 12/2017/TT-BGDĐT, dated May 19, 2017, of the Ministry of Education and Training on promulgating regulations on accreditation of higher education institutions.
- xviii Nguyen Duc Tri (2011), *Vocational Education Curriculum*, Vietnam Education Publishing House.
- xix Nguyen Duc Tri - Ho Ngoc Vinh (2013), *Teaching methods in vocational training*, Vietnam Education Publishing House.
- xx Aaker, D.A., (2003). *The power of the branded differentiator*. MIT Sloan Management Review, Fall: 83-7.
- xxi Aaker, D.A., (2004). *Leveraging the corporate brand*. California Management Review, 46:6-18.
- xxii Abrantes, J. L., Seabra, C., & Lages, L. F. (2007). *Pedagogical affect, student interest, and learning performance*. *Journal of Business Research*, 60(9), 960-964.

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- xxiii Adewale, O.O. and Anthonia, A.A., 2013. *Impact of Organizational Culture on Human Resource Practices: A Study of Selected Nigerian Private Universities*. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 5:115-133.
- xxiv Ansari Saleh Ahmar et al (2018), *Lecturers' Understanding on Indexing Databases of SINTA, DOAJ, Google Scholar, SCOPUS, and Web of Science: A Study of Indonesians*, *Journal of Physics: Conf. Series* 954.
- xxv Appleton-Knapp, S.L. và Krentler, K.A., 2006. *Measuring Student Expectations and Their Effects on Satisfaction: The Importance of Managing Student Expectations*. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 28:254-264.
- xxvi Beneke (2011), Baumgartner, Hans, Mita Sujana, and Dan Padgett (1997), *Pattern of Affective Reactions to Advertisements. The Intergeration of Moment-to Moment Responses into Overall Judgments*. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34,219- 232.
- xxvii Burmann, C., Zeplin, S., 2005. *Building brand commitment: a behavioral approach to internal brand management*. *J. Brand Manag.* 12 (4), 279e300.
- xxviii Burmann, C., Zeplin, S., Riley, N., 2009. *Key determinants of internal brand management success: an exploratory empirical analysis*. *J. Brand Manag.* 16, 264e284.
- xxix Dr. Habes Moh'd Hatamleh (2016), *Obstacles of Scientific Research with Faculty of University of Jadara from Their Point of View*, *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol.7, No.33, p. 32-47.
- xxx Drs. H. Akbar Ali, M.Si. (2015), *Performance Lecturer's Competence As The Quality Assurance*, *The International Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol 30, No 1.
- xxxi King, Ceridwyn, Grace, Debra (2010), *Building and Measuring Employee- Based Brand Equity*, *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 44 No. 7/8, pp. 938-971.
- xxxii Mohammed m. A., huda i. And maslinda m. N. (2015), *Electronic information sharing between public universities and ministry of higher education and scientific research: A pilot study*, *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, Vol. 77 No.1,
- xxxiii Molefe, G.N. (2010), *Performance measurement dimensions for lecturers at selected universities: An international perspective*, *SA Journal of Human Resource Management/ SA Tydskrif vir Menslikehulpbronbestuur*, 8(1), 13 pages. DOI: 10.4102/sajhrm. v8i1.243.
- xxxiv Virgil K. Rowland (2012). *Enhancing learning outcomes: the effects of instructional technology, learning style, instructional methods*. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 25(2), 130-142.